

A Study on Students Factors Influencing the Drop Out in Government Primary Education Schools in Telangna State

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Abstract:

Education is forms of the foundation of every society, the quality of education imparted in educational institutions should be elevating any nation. Education plays a vital role in shaping the future of a country and meeting its growing demands, thereby creating a healthy and progressive society. It is noticed that every government makes the consistent efforts for the promotion of the whole development of its future citizens. However, one of the main barriers to ensuring that every Indian has access to education is the country's persistently high dropout rates. The current study explores the possible reasons for dropouts and suggests solutions to curb this danger. This study was carried out in the Hyderabad district with a sample size of 100 parents from of schools government schools This study revealed that government schools have higher dropout rates to other schools.

Keywords: socio economic profile, primary education, School Drop out

1.Introduction:

Education empowers the younger generation with historical knowledge and contemporary tools to shape the future and is the cornerstone for human advancement towards building a wholesome society. It makes individuals progressive and rational thinkers and helps in the acquisition of knowledge and expertise to escape intergenerational poverty and get a better career. The goal of India's school education vision 2030 is to provide all children in the school-attending age group with a high-quality education. However, dropout is a major issue. Dropout happens when a student leaves a school or a college before completing their academic programme. It is a serious issue that impacts students all over and can have negative repercussions in their lives. India suffers due to this malady, which is cause for considerable concern.

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The development of society depends on quality education and it can only be measured by assessing the socio-economic indicators that extend educational inequality prevalent in society. Many factors contribute to the unequal distribution of education among urban and rural India. The government had ensured to reach the goal of achieving basic education for all by 2010 utilizing *Sarva Shiksha Abhiyan* and Right to Education initiatives. Access to education and school enrolment rates at all levels were subsequently increased, but the phenomenon of school dropouts still plagues the progress of education in India. It is of utmost concern that high dropout rates were reported in most states in India at all stages, despite major efforts, school attendance rates primary levels, Illiteracy, poverty, inadequate earnings and poor living conditions of parents force them to withdraw and also put them into various low paid jobs to contribute to the family income. The percentage of students who drop out of school has either climbed or stayed the same during the past few years, despite an increase in enrollment rates. The secondary level dropout rate (17%) is still high compared to the primary level (1.8%) and upper primary level (1.5%). Education is a fundamental human right. It is a key factor in the continued economic development of the country and its ability to enhance the quality of life for its citizens as well as compete within global world markets (Okumu, et al, 2008). The problem of dropout has always been persistent in all the developing countries. The National Education Policy (2020) aims to meet the inadequacies concerning quality education, innovation and research.

The state statistical analysis has been to achieve equity of elementary education that indicates both discontinued children during the primary school-going age and the children who were forced to terminate their education before completion of primary school due to social and economic obligations. Several studies have been conducted on dropout issues based on different gender, region, in various parts of the world. This paper has tried to investigation several factors which can broadly be divided into , economic factors, household-level factors , caste and gender-based factors , cultural and regional factors.

2. Review of Literature:

Syed Rooquiyya Tabassum, (2019) The dropout rate is also influenced by ignorant and illiterate parents. Unlike educated parents, ignorant and illiterate parents don't constitute for their children's

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regularity at school. However, most of the illiterate parents aspire big for their children. A considerable amount of them is still responsible for school dropouts. This might be due to a lack of information about formal school education which they have never been subjected to. The involvement of parents in school academic affairs plays a magnificent role. The more a parent intervenes in his or her child's education, the less are the chances of child dropouts.

Tabassum (2019) reported that the school dropout rate remains consistently high for boys in comparisons to girls, and this study identified some of the reasons for dropouts, such as lack of interest in studies, domestic contribution of children for household chores, economic reasons, and migration of families. In their investigation into the reasons for the low enrollment of students in government elementary schools,

Mohalik, Sethy, and Sangeeta (2021) discovered that factors like the involvement of both parents in the workforce, children's involvement in domestic work, taking care of younger siblings, parents' relocation for employment, children's involvement in farming and harvesting, parents' low aspirations, an abusive home environment, students' lack of interest in academics, their lack of basic skills, and the lack of teachers and regular head teachers among others.

Sembiah, and Biswas (2018) assessed the degree and causes of school absenteeism and analysed the predictors of absenteeism in a slum community in Kolkata. The data analysis revealed that 43 percent of the children who went to school had been absent for more than two days in the previous month, with the main reasons being illness (18.98%), rainy days (16.45%), and social or family occasions (11.28%). The analysis of literature in general reveals that the increase in dropout rates among students is due to the following factors: economic condition, lack of proper infrastructure, migration, lack of teachers, communication, and the poor health of the students triggered by ignorance of hygiene and insufficient accessibility of health services.

Das and Saha (2014) reported that the northern districts of West Bengal have a much lower dropout rate than the southern districts, with the exception being Bankura and Purulia. Their analysis showed that migration, lack of parental education, large family size, and poverty worsen the dropout problems.

3.Objectives of the study:

1. To study the demographic profile of parents in primary education Schools.
2. To analyse the factors effecting school dropouts at the Primary education Schools.
3. To suggest measures that would reduce the number of school dropouts

4. Methodology

The purpose of the study is to examine how the different socio-economic factors Determine and influence the rate of dropouts in India and compare the relationship between different socio-economic factors. Descriptive design was used for the present study. This study is based on literature survey and field investigation using a standard questionnaire.

Statistical Tolls : The Study data is tablated and analysed using the MS Excel, such as Percentage, Correlation.

Sample Size: Sample size of 100 parents from of schools government schools and private schools.

5.Interpretation of the Data

H01: Lack of School Fees are is not impacting on Monthly Income of Parent, Educational Qualification, Occupation of the Parents and drop out of students

Table-1 Lack of School Fees are is not impacting on Monthly Income of Parent, Educational Qualification, Occupation of the Parents and drop out of students

Model Summary						
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate		
1	.058 ^a	.003	-.025	1.28843		
a. Predictors: (Constant), Monthly Income of Parent, Educational Qualification, Occupation of the Parent:						
ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	.590	3	.197	.119	.949 ^b
	Residual	175.964	106	1.660		
	Total	176.555	109			
a. Dependent Variable: Lack of School Fees						

b. Predictors: (Constant), Monthly Income of Parent, Educational Qualification, Occupation of the Parent:

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	3.153	.386		8.174	.000
	Educational Qualification	-.059	.104	-.065	-.562	.575
	Occupation of the Parent	.019	.135	.016	.139	.890
	Monthly Income of Parent	.011	.113	.009	.095	.925

a. Dependent Variable: Lack of School Fees

From that above regression table as R represents the correlation between dependent variable and independent variable, it can identified that the relationship between independent variables Monthly income , Educational Qualification and occupation of parents are positive correlation.

It can be noted that they have correlated at Low degree since R value is 0.094 which is greater than 0.05 significant levels. It can evidenced that the coefficient of determination is 0.009 therefore about 0.9% of the variation in impact of Lack of School Fees.

The ANOVA is used to evaluate the certainty of a linear relationship between variables. According to this output, F=0.316 at 5% significance level p value is 0.814 which is greater than 0.05. It could be concluded that at a significance level of 5% there is no significant difference between the dependent variable Lack of School Fees and the independent variable Monthly Income of Parent, Educational Qualification, Occupation of the Parent.

We can conclude that that there exists enough evidence to prove the existence of relationship between school dropout of students and health problems and Monthly Income of Parent, Educational Qualification, Occupation of the Parent. t value is 8.174 at 5% significant level p value 0.00. Hence it concludes that there is a significant Lack of School Fees and Monthly Income of Parent, Educational Qualification, Occupation of the Parent. The regression equation presents the impact of independent variables on dependent variable as shown

Y (Lack of School Fees) = b_1x educational qualification + $b_2 x$ Occupation of parents + $b_3 x$ Monthly income.

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$Y(\text{Lack of School Fees}) = 3.153 + (-0.059)(\text{Educational Qualification}) + 0.019(\text{Occupation of the Parent}) + 0.011(\text{Monthly Income of Parent})$

Ho2: Death of Parents are is not impacting on Monthly Income of Parent, Educational Qualification, Occupation of the Parents and drop out of students

Model Summary						
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate		
1	.158 ^a	.025	-.003	1.17810		
a. Predictors: (Constant), Monthly Income of Parent, Educational Qualification, Occupation of the Parent:						
ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	3.754	3	1.251	.902	.443 ^b
	Residual	147.118	106	1.388		
	Total	150.873	109			
a. Dependent Variable: Death of Parents						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Monthly Income of Parent, Educational Qualification, Occupation of the Parent:						
Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.232	.353		6.328	.000
	Educational Qualification	.011	.096	.014	.119	.906
	Occupation of the Parent:	.162	.123	.151	1.313	.192
	Monthly Income of Parent	.032	.103	.031	.313	.755
a. Dependent Variable: Death of Parents						

From that above regression table as R represents the correlation between dependent variable and independent variables, it can identify that the relationship between independent variables Monthly income, Educational Qualification and occupation of parents are positive correlation.

It can be noted that they have correlated at Low degree since R value is 0.158 which is greater than 0.05 significant levels. It can evidenced that the coefficient of determination is 0.025 therefore about 2.5% of the variation in impact of Death of Parents.

The ANOVA is used to evaluate the certainty of a linear relationship between variables. According to this output, F=0.902 at 5% significance level p value is 0.443 which is greater than 0.05. It could be concluded that at a significance level of 5% there is no significant difference between the dependent variable Death of Parents and the independent variables Monthly Income of Parent, Educational Qualification, Occupation of the Parent.

We can conclude that that there exists enough evidence to prove the existence of relationship between school dropout of students and Death of parents and Monthly Income of Parent, Educational Qualification, Occupation of the Parent. t value is 6.328 at 5% significant level p value 0.00. hence it conclude that there is a significant Death of parents and Monthly Income of Parent, Educational Qualification, Occupation of the Parent. The regression equation presents the impact of independent variables on dependent variable as shown

Y (Death of parents) = $b_1 \times$ educational qualification + $b_2 \times$ Occupation of parents + $b_3 \times$ Monthly income.

Y (Death of parents) = 2.232 + 0.011(Educational Qualification) + 0.162(Occupation of the Parent) + 0.032(Monthly Income of Parent)

Ho3: Health problems are is not impacting on Monthly Income of Parent, Educational Qualification, Occupation of the Parents and drop out of students

Model Summary						
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate		
1	.094 ^a	.009	-.019	1.13354		
a. Predictors: (Constant), Monthly Income of Parent, Educational Qualification, Occupation of the Parent:						
ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	1.218	3	.406	.316	.814 ^b

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	Residual	136.200	106	1.285		
	Total	137.418	109			
a. Dependent Variable: Health Problems						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Monthly Income of Parent, Educational Qualification, Occupation of the Parent:						
Coefficients^a						
		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients		
Model		B	Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.
1	(Constant)	3.078	.339		9.070	.000
	Educational Qualification	-.068	.092	-.085	-.740	.461
	Occupation of the Parent:	-.013	.119	-.012	-.107	.915
	Monthly Income of Parent	.022	.099	.022	.221	.826
a. Dependent Variable: Health Problems						

From that above regression table as R represents the correlation between dependent variable and independent variables, it can identify that the relationship between independent variables Monthly income, Educational Qualification and occupation of parents are positive correlation.

It can be noted that they have correlated at Low degree since R value is 0.094 which is greater than 0.05 significant levels. It can evidenced that the coefficient of determination is 0.009 therefore about 0.9% of the variation in impact of Health Problems .

The ANOVA is used to evaluate the certainty of a linear relationship between variables. According to this output, F=0.316 at 5% significance level p value is 0.814 which is greater than 0.05. It could be concluded that at a significance level of 5% there is no significant difference between the dependent variable Health Problems and the independent variables Monthly Income of Parent, Educational Qualification, Occupation of the Parent.

We can conclude that that there exists enough evidence to prove the existence of relationship between school dropout of students and Health Problems and Monthly Income of Parent, Educational Qualification, Occupation of the Parent. t value is 9.070 at 5% significant level p value 0.00. Hence it concludes that there is a significant Health Problems and Monthly Income

of Parent, Educational Qualification, Occupation of the Parent. The regression equation presents the impact of independent variables on dependent variable as shown

Y (Health Problems) = $b_1 \times$ educational qualification + $b_2 \times$ Occupation of parents + $b_3 \times$ Monthly income.

Y (Health Problems) = 3.078 + (-0.068)(Educational Qualification) + (-0.013)(Occupation of the Parent) + 0.022(Monthly Income of Parent)

Ho4: Lack of School infrastructure are is not impacting on Monthly Income of Parent, Educational Qualification, Occupation of the Parents and drop out of students

Model Summary						
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate		
1	.212 ^a	.045	.018	1.15447		
a. Predictors: (Constant), Monthly Income of Parent, Educational Qualification, Occupation of the Parent:						
ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	6.623	3	2.208	1.656	.181 ^b
	Residual	141.277	106	1.333		
	Total	147.900	109			
a. Dependent Variable: Lack of school infrastructure						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Monthly Income of Parent, Educational Qualification, Occupation of the Parent:						
Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.186	.346		6.326	.000
	Educational Qualification	.005	.094	.006	.053	.957
	Occupation of the Parent:	.164	.121	.154	1.356	.178
	Monthly Income of Parent	.170	.101	.163	1.683	.095
a. Dependent Variable: Lack of school infrastructure						

From that above regression table as R represents the correlation between dependent variable and independent variables, it can identify that the relationship between independent variables Monthly income, Educational Qualification and occupation of parents are positive correlation.

It can be noted that they have correlated at Low degree since R value is 0.212 which is greater than 0.05 significant levels. It can evidence that the coefficient of determination is 0.045 therefore about 4.5% of the variation in impact of Health Problems.

The ANOVA is used to evaluate the certainty of a linear relationship between variables. According to this output, $F=1.656$ at 5% significance level p value is 0.181 which is greater than 0.05. It could be concluded that at a significance level of 5% there is no significant difference between the dependent variable Lack of School infrastructure and the independent variables Monthly Income of Parent, Educational Qualification, Occupation of the Parent.

We can conclude that that there exists enough evidence to prove the existence of relationship between school dropout of students and Lack of School infrastructure and Monthly Income of Parent, Educational Qualification, Occupation of the Parent. t value is 6.326 at 5% significant level p value 0.00. Hence it concludes that there is a significant Lack of School infrastructure and Monthly Income of Parent, Educational Qualification, Occupation of the Parent. The regression equation presents the impact of independent variables on dependent variable as shown

Y (Lack of School infrastructure) = b_1x educational qualification + $b_2 x$ Occupation of parents + $b_3 x$ Monthly income.

Y (Lack of School infrastructure) = $2.186+0.005(\text{Educational Qualification})+0.164(\text{Occupation of the Parent})+0.170(\text{Monthly Income of Parent})$

6. Findings/Findings and Conclusion:

1. Government should devise ways and means to control the population and educate people about the consequences of population explosion. It cannot be denied that the government is already doing this in India however; the fact remains that much needs to be accomplished.

2. Child Labour which is banned by the Indian Government is still now practiced in certain areas. It is recommended that the government should look deeper and check the implementation of their policies properly conducts awareness programmers in rural areas and expose the hazards of such situations to the parents.
3. Government should launch more programs where they can provide free education to more children in the villages follows the quality of mid-day meals should be developed to increase the attainment of children.
4. Children in India fall sick mostly due to sanitation problems, government should focus on improving the surroundings of the child as a strong mind cannot survive in a weak body'. The toilets in rural areas, which leads to health problems and the government should implement more policies and look into the matter.
5. Good infrastructure should be established in schools so as to draw students closer to education and spark interest in them.
6. Due to lack of transportation parents cannot send their children to the schools which are located far from their home. Government should set up schools which are easily accessible to children.

Conclusion

Dropouts at the school level in India are a serious matter of concern. While India is Moving forward towards ensuring 'admission for all' with the Right to Education, concerns for the dropouts as serious as children belonging to the relevant age-cohort and not enrolling. Dropouts result in wastage of the education system thereby proving it to be inefficient. Closer to half of the population in India chose to discontinue its studies after the primary education level . The study has also observed the parental characteristics which possibly influenced the dropout rates play a crucial role in determining quality education. It is significant to highlight that refining the school infrastructure, quality of education and better efficient investment in quality education can prevent the dropouts to a limited range. Unless and until there is considerable improvement in the economic status of households and change in the social attitudes of parents, achieving the goal of school education will remain a major challenge for India.

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